

Implementation of Law Number 42 Year 1999 in the Execution of Fiducia Securities

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Abstract

Along with the development of the business, there have been so many facilitators who offer credit to companies or individuals. Meanwhile, if you hear the word credit, it is not far from accounts receivable, where accounts receivable or other transactions cannot be based on the principle of trust alone. Therefore, it must be accompanied by a guarantee that convinces the interested parties, both the debtor and the creditor, in the form of a fiduciary guarantee. The definition of fiduciary according to article 1 point (1) of Law Number 42 of 1999 reads "fiduciary is the transfer of ownership rights to an object on the basis of belief with the stipulation that the object whose ownership rights are transferred remains under the control of the owner of the object". Meanwhile, the definition of fiduciary security according to article 1 point (2) is "fiduciary security is the right to movable objects, both tangible and intangible and immovable objects, especially buildings that cannot be encumbered with Mortgage Rights as referred to in Law Number 4 of 1996. concerning Mortgage Rights (Law No.4 of 1996 concerning Mortgage Rights) which remains under the control of the Fiduciary, as collateral for the settlement of certain debts, which gives the Fiduciary priority over other creditors ". Fiduciary agreements are generally stated in the form of a notary deed with the aim of providing legal certainty. In practice, the use of this fiduciary guarantee institution is very often used by companies, banks or individual interests, with the aim of securing assets in a credit agreement. Thus, the binding of an object with a fiduciary guarantee prior to the existence of a credit agreement as the principal agreement. In the activities of these accounts payable it is also not uncommon if there is no event of default where there must be execution of the goods that are the object of the fiduciary security.

Keywords: *implementation, execution, assurance, fiduciary*

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the development of fiduciary is quite pleasing to its users because it was originally regulated in jurisprudence and then received recognition in Law Number 16 of 1985. The regulation of fiduciary institutions in the Law on Flats is still vague, but sufficient to provide legal certainty in particular. concerning understanding and fiduciary objects In the Flat Law, fiduciary is defined as a guarantee in the form of the transfer of rights over property based on trust and agreed as a guarantee for the repayment of creditors' receivables. This formulation does not yet reveal the material characteristics of a fiduciary institution, for example the position of fiduciary creditors to other creditors (preferred creditors). In addition, it does not explain the nature of the handover which is the characteristic feature of fiduciary, namely the transferred object remains with the fiduciary, nor does it mention what is transferred to the creditor because this is also an important element of fiduciary, namely ownership in the form of non-material rights.

It is also not clearly stated what objects are delivered, but it can be understood that what is meant is including flats and ownership rights to apartment units established on land use rights over State land. The development of the Fiduciary legislation in Indonesia was very slow and it was only promulgated on September 30, 1999 regarding the roll-out of reforms in Indonesia, namely law number 42 of 1999 concerning the Fiduciary Guarantee.

Fiduciary is the transfer of ownership rights to an object based on trust provided that the object whose ownership rights are transferred is under the control of the owner of the goods (Article 1 number 1 of the Goods Guarantee Law). Fiduciary Guarantee is the right of immovable objects, both tangible and intangible, and immovable objects, especially buildings that cannot be encumbered by the Mortgage Rights as referred to in Law Number 4 of 1996 concerning Mortgage Rights which remain under the control of the fiduciary repayment of certain debts, which give priority to the recipient of fiduciary against other creditors (Article 1 point 2 of the Goods Guarantee Law). Giver of fiduciary is an individual or corporation that owns the object which is the object of the object (Article 1 point 5 of the Goods Guarantee Law). Fiduciary recipients are individuals or corporations having receivables whose payment is guaranteed by Fiduciary security (Article 1 number 6 of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law).

RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research used in this writing is a type of normative legal research which only examines the laws and regulations. Sources of data used in this paper are primary data in the form of laws and legal literatures and several cases related to Fiduciary Security in Indonesia. This type of approach in writing is a statutory approach (The Statute Approach). This study uses a qualitative method with a literature review approach (library research), which is collecting data or scientific papers related to the object of research or collecting library data. This study explores the implementation of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law in Indonesia. The author uses some of the latest materials, including the latest manuscript on Fiduciary Security in Indonesia, the latest data on Fiduciary cases, organizational websites (professional, health and government), formal news (online). As well as conducting analytic interpretations with strict verification, the aim is to see the suitability of the manuscripts with the context of the current case (Gentles et al., 2016; Schyren, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, legislators do not explicitly state the legal principles of fiduciary security which are the foundation of the formation of legal norms, but in fact the legal principles of fiduciary security can be found in the articles of the Fiduciary Guarantee Act. The legal principles of fiduciary security contained in the Fiduciary Guarantee Act are:

1. Droit de preference principle

The creditor of the fiduciary recipient is the creditor that takes precedence over other creditors. This principle can be found in Article 1 point 2 further the Fiduciary Guarantee Law does not provide an understanding of what is meant by a creditor that takes precedence over other creditors. However, in another section, namely Article 27 of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, it explains the definition of prioritized rights against other creditors. Priority right is the right of the fiduciary recipient to take repayment of his claim on the result of the execution of the object which is the object of the fiduciary security.

2. The principle of the droit de suite

The fiduciary guarantee still follows the object which is the object of the fiduciary guarantee in the hands of whoever the object is located. In law, this principle is called "droit de suite". The recognition of this principle in the Fiduciary Guarantee Act shows that fiduciary security is a material right (zakelijkrecht) and not an individual right (persoonlijkrecht.) Thus, the fiduciary security can be maintained against anyone. also and has the right to sue anyone who violates these rights.

Individual rights do not have the character of the droit de suite. In the character of droit de suite there is a principle that the rights of the old take precedence over the rights of the young. This means that if there are several material rights placed on an object, the power of that right is determined by the sequence of time. Recognition of the principle that the fiduciary security right follows the object in the hands of whomever the object is in provides legal certainty for the creditor holding the fiduciary security to obtain payment of the debt from the sale of the fiduciary security object if the debtor guarantees fiduciary in default. The legal certainty of these rights is not only that the fiduciary object remains with the debtor who provides the fiduciary guarantee even when the fiduciary property is in the possession of a third party.

The material rights of the new fiduciary security are born on the date when the fiduciary security is recorded in the fiduciary register. Therefore, the juridical consequence is that the implementation of the droit de suite principle will only be recognized since the date of recording of the fiduciary security in the fiduciary register. The purpose of this affirmation is none other than that if the fiduciary guarantee is not recorded in the fiduciary register, it means that the fiduciary security right is not a material right but has the character of an individual right. As a result, for third parties, the fiduciary security rights of the creditors holding the fiduciary guarantee are not respected. As a consequence, if there is a transfer of fiduciary collateral, the creditors holding the fiduciary guarantee cannot be protected based on the droit de suite principle. In other words, the creditor holding the fiduciary security is a concurrent creditor, not a preferred creditor.

3. Principle of Priority

The fiduciary guarantee is a follow-up agreement which is commonly referred to as a priority. This principle implies that the existence of a fiduciary guarantee is determined by another agreement, namely the main agreement or principal agreement. The main agreement for fiduciary security is a debt-receivable agreement that gives birth to debt which is secured by fiduciary security. In the UUJF, this principle is explicitly stated that the fiduciary guarantee is a covenant of a principal agreement. In accordance with the nature of this assessor, the termination of the fiduciary guarantee is also determined by the write-off of the debt or by the repayment of the right to the fiduciary guarantee by the creditor receiving the fiduciary guarantee.

4. Principle of Specialty or Affection

That the fiduciary guarantee contains a detailed description of the subject and object of the fiduciary guarantee. The subject of the fiduciary guarantee contains a detailed description of the subject of the fiduciary guarantee. The subject of the fiduciary guarantee in question is the identity of the parties, namely the giver and recipient of the fiduciary account, while the guarantee object referred to is the data on the principal agreement guaranteed to be fiduciary, a description of the fiduciary collateral object, the guarantee value and the value of the object which is the object of the guarantee. In the science of law it is called the principle of specialty or explanation.

5. Publication Principles

The Fiduciary Guarantee must be registered with the Fiduciary Registration Office. In law, it is called the principle of publication. With the enactment of the fiduciary security deed registration, it means that the fiduciary agreement was born and the momentum shows that the fiduciary guarantee agreement is a material agreement. The principle of publication also creates legal certainty from fiduciary guarantees

6. Principle of Confession

Objects that are used as the object of fiduciary security cannot be owned by the creditor who receives the fiduciary guarantee even if it is agreed upon.

7. The Fiduciary Guarantee gives priority rights to creditors who receive fiduciaries who register first at the Fiduciary Office rather than creditors who register later.

8. Principle of Good Faith

The fiduciary must have good faith. The principle of good faith here has a subjective meaning as a continuation, not an objective meaning as obedience such as compliance as in contract law. With this principle it

is expected that the fiduciary guarantor is obliged to maintain the collateral object, not transfer, lease and mortgage to other parties.

9. The Fiduciary Guarantee Principle is easy to execute

The ease of execution of the fiduciary guarantee is carried out by including the irah-irah: For the sake of Justice based on One Godhead "on the fiduciary guarantee certificate. With this executorial title, it creates juridical consequences that fiduciary guarantees have the same legal force as court decisions that have permanent legal force.

Abolition of Fiduciary Guarantee

What is meant by the termination of the fiduciary guarantee is that the fiduciary guarantee is no longer valid. There are 3 reasons for the termination of the fiduciary guarantee, namely:

1. Write-off of debt guaranteed by fiduciary. What is meant by debt write-off is due to, among others, due to repayment and proof of debt write-off in the form of information made by the editor.
2. Waiver of fiduciary security rights by the fiduciary.
3. The destruction of objects that are the object of fiduciary security. The destruction of fiduciary collateral does not erase the claim of insurance (Article 25 of Law Number 42 of 1999).

Age of age, proxies or representatives to notify in writing to the Fiduciary Registration Office of the write-off of principal debt. Such notification is not later than 7 days after the termination of the fiduciary security concerned, enclosing supporting documents regarding the abolition of the fiduciary regime. With the receipt of the notification, 2 things will be done by the Fiduciary Registration Office, namely:

1. At the same time write off fiduciary security from the fiduciary register
2. On the same date as the date of the withdrawal of fiduciary security from the fiduciary register book. The fiduciary registration office issues a certificate stating *the fiduciary guarantee certificate concerned is no longer valid*.

Fiduciary Guarantee Execution Procedure

1. Procedure for Withdrawal of Motor Vehicles that are the object of Fiduciary Security

If the debtor defaults (in the sense that he does not fulfill his obligation to pay installments of at least 3 (three) times, the creditor must first go through a warning process, namely a warning letter so that he / she will fulfill his obligations. If after being warned he does not fulfill his obligations, then by referring to the Creditor's Fiduciary Agreement Deed by making a written warning letter which essentially states that because the debtor has defaulted, referring to the Fiduciary Agreement Deed, the debtor is asked within a grace period of one day (for example 7 days) to voluntarily submit the object of guarantee fiduciary (stated as a fiduciary object, for example a car / motorbike with a police number) to the creditor, if within the specified time period the debtor does not want to voluntarily hand over the fiduciary object, the creditor, assisted by the Police of the Police, will conduct an investigation. pulling a fiduciary object by force

The procedure for withdrawing fiduciary objects must refer to Regulation of the Chief of Police No. 8 of 2011, which is done by the creditor or proxies must file a written application for securing the execution of the withdrawal of fiduciary objects, which is addressed to the local Police Chief by attaching the following conditions: a). a copy of the fiduciation guarantee deed; b). copy of fiduciation guarantee certificate; c). A warning letter to the debtor to fulfill obligations; d). The identity of the executor,

A warning letter to the debtor to fulfill the obligations. Execution assignment letter.

1. Make an appeal to unauthorized parties to leave the execution location
2. Carry out tight security when there is dialogue and negotiation between the executor and the executor
3. Protect the executor and / or the executed applicant and the people at the location.
4. Observe, supervise and mark people who attempt to obstruct or obstruct execution
5. Secure and supervise objects / or items to be executed

If the execution runs safely, orderly and smoothly, the security personnel will act passively, but if there is resistance from the executed party, the security personnel must be active by taking the following actions:

1. Securing and or arresting every person who takes resistance or acts against the law
2. Conduct searches of any person suspected of carrying firearms, sharp weapons and other dangerous objects
3. Confiscating sharp weapons and other dangerous objects obtained at the execution site
4. Localizing and or blocking road access to and from the execution site

If during the execution of the withdrawal of the object of fiduciary security based on the information from the debtor, he feels that he has paid off his obligations to another officer appointed by the applicant for execution, then the personnel of the Police who carry out the security can take the following actions:

1. Perform persuasive action between the applicant and the respondent through deliberation
2. Asking politely and humanely to the respondent to show proof of payment or repayment documents
3. Secure the environment around the execution to prevent any escalation in security
4. If the termoho has proof of payment or settlement, the police personnel take action to delay or stop the execution and bring the respondent and the applicant for the execution to the nearest Police Office for further handling.

In carrying out the withdrawal of the fiduciary object, the executing officer of the withdrawal ordered by the company must act persuasively and physical violence must be avoided, but if this approach has been taken, it

turns out that the debtor is actually making threats or acts of violence, then the police apparatus who accompanies it must secure the concerned.

As for the elements of the provisions of Article 36 of Law No. 42 of 1999 as follows:

1. Giver of Fiduciary
2. Those who transfer, pawn, or lease objects that are the object of fiduciary security as referred to in Article 23 paragraph (2) which are carried out without the prior written consent of the Fiduciary recipient (imprisonment for a maximum of 2 (two) years and a maximum fine of Rp.50,000. .000).

Fiduciary Guarantee Procedure, if the debtor defaults. The procedure (procedure) for the execution of the Fiduciary Guarantee is regulated in the provisions of Article 29 of the UUJF, which are as follows:

The first method, the implementation is based on the executorial title outlined in Article 15 paragraph (2) of the Law

- The recipient of Fiduciary can exercise the right to sell the object of the fiduciary security on his own power
- The method is to directly sell the object of fiduciary security without going through court
- However, on condition that the sale must go through a public auction by the Auction Office / Auction Officer
- As well as the right to take debt repayment from the sale proceeds by overriding the concurrent creditors based on the preference rights they have

The implementation of fiduciary practices, as it has been explained that the Fiduciary Guarantee makes it easy for parties who use it, especially for the Fiduciary Giver. On the contrary, because the Fiduciary Guarantee does not guarantee the Execution of the Fiduciary Guarantee. However, it is still an important note that the main problem of how debt collectors execute fiduciary collateral by means of violence, intimidation and even seizing fiduciary goods on the road, are still part of a separate scourge that cannot be separated in the practice of executing fiduciary guarantees.

This is where the execution process is no longer regulated, but the company's obedience in carrying out the execution. Companies in the provisions of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law must be directed to comply with good and correct legal principles, not just transferring responsibility to company membership and accountability then transferring to subordinates. This has been the main problem so far.

Before this Law was enacted, in general, objects that were objects of Fiduciary Security were movable objects consisting of items in inventory, merchandise, receivables, machine tools, and motorized vehicles. Therefore, in order to meet the needs of a growing community, according to this Law the objects of the Fiduciary Guarantee are given a broad and broad definition, namely movable objects, tangible or intangible, and immovable objects that cannot be encumbered with a liability as stipulated in Law Number 4 of 1996 concerning Mortgage Rights.

CONCLUSION

Fiduciary can be defined as one of the parties who has tied himself up and gives the right of ownership to his movable object to the party concerned who will be granted this right. Meanwhile, the definition of fiduciary security according to article 1 point (2) is "fiduciary security is the right to movable objects, both tangible and intangible and immovable objects, especially buildings that cannot be encumbered with the Mortgage Rights as referred to in Law No. 4 of Year. 1996 concerning Mortgage Rights which remain in the control of the Fiduciary, as collateral for the settlement of certain debts, which give the Fiduciary priority over other creditors ". This Fiduciary binding agreement originates from the existence of accounts receivable between the creditor and the debtor where this agreement aims to anticipate if the creditor is in default to pay off its debts.

This fiduciary agreement is usually stated in the form of a notary deed, in order to convince the parties concerned in entering into an agreement. Fiduciary Security Execution is an activity to confiscate and sell objects that are the object of fiduciary security. The execution in this civil case is carried out based on the request of the party that is declared victorious by the Judge's decision, starting with a warning given by the Head of the District Court to the party who is declared a loser to carry out the decision voluntarily within days and given a due date. In principle, the execution of the Fiduciary Guarantee is of a special nature, considering that previously the object has been agreed upon by the debtor, however the condition of the Fiduciary Security object, even though the object is a means of earning a living, will still be executed. Fiduciary registration is carried out directly by the fiduciary recipient or anyone authorized to represent the implementation of registration at the Fiduciary Registration Office.

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